

1 **Plant attributes explain the distribution of soil microbial communities in two contrasting regions**
2 **of the globe.**

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28

29 **Brief heading:** Plant attributes drive soil microbial communities across two contrasting regions of
30 Earth

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32 **Summary**

- 33 • We lack strong empirical evidence for links between plant attributes (plant community
34 attributes and functional traits) and the distribution of soil microbial communities at large
35 spatial scales.
- 36 • Using datasets from two contrasting regions and ecosystem types in Australia and England, we
37 report that aboveground plant community attributes such as diversity (species richness), cover,
38 and functional traits can predict a unique portion of the variation in the diversity (number of
39 phylotypes) and community composition of soil bacteria and fungi, that cannot be explained
40 by soil abiotic properties and climate. We further identify the relative importance and evaluate
41 the potential direct and indirect effects of climate, soil properties and plant attributes in
42 regulating the diversity and community composition of soil microbial communities.
- 43 • Finally, we deliver a list of examples including common taxa from Australia and England that
44 are strongly related to specific plant traits, such as specific leaf area index, leaf N, and N
45 fixation.
- 46 • Together, our work provides new evidence that plant attributes, especially plant functional
47 traits, can predict the distribution soil microbial communities at the regional scale and across
48 two hemispheres.

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50 Key words: Plant functional traits; Bacteria; Fungi; Biodiversity; Terrestrial ecosystems.

51 **Introduction**

52 Soil microbial communities play important roles in driving multiple ecosystem functions and services
53 including climate regulation, nutrient cycling, water regulation, and food and fibre production
54 (Bardgett & van der Putten 2014; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2017). Previous studies have provided
55 evidence that abiotic factors such as climate (Maestre *et al.* 2015; Zhou *et al.* 2016) and soil chemical
56 properties (pH, soil carbon and nutrients; Lauber *et al.* 2009; Maestre *et al.* 2015; Tedersoo *et al.* 2014)
57 are the main predictors of the distribution of soil microbial communities across the globe. Much less
58 is known, however, about the role of plant attributes including community-level attributes, such as
59 diversity and cover, and functional traits in regulating the distribution of soil microbial communities
60 at regional scales (i.e., hundreds of kilometers). Identifying the relative importance of plant attributes
61 in predicting the distribution of soil microbial communities is of paramount importance, as plant
62 communities are highly sensitive to climate, N enrichment, and land use intensification (Allan *et al.*
63 2015; Le Bagousse-Pinguet *et al.* 2017), and resulting shifts in vegetation might have cascading effects
64 on the diversity and functioning of soil microbial communities (García-Palacios *et al.* 2016; Deraison
65 *et al.* 2015; Le Bagousse-Pinguet *et al.* 2017).

66 The identity of plant genotypes or lichen species, major biological components of cold and
67 warm deserts, has recently been highlighted as a major predictor of the distribution of soil bacteria at
68 the local scale (Leff *et al.* 2017; Liu *et al.* 2017). Much less is known, however, about the role of other
69 plant attributes such as plant diversity (number of species), plant cover, and plant functional traits as
70 predictors of the diversity (number of phylotypes) and community composition of soil bacterial and
71 fungal communities. While empirical evidence is lacking, the conceptual links among plant attributes
72 and microbial community composition are reasonably well established (Hooper *et al.* 2000; Wardle *et*
73 *al.* 2004; Lavorel 2013; Bardgett 2017). Plant community attributes and functional traits can directly
74 affect soil microbes by altering the quality (which can be represented by measures such as specific
75 leaf area –SLA– and tissue nutrient content; Cornelissen *et al.* 2003) and quantity of resource inputs
76 *via* litter and detritus (which can be represented via measures such as plant biomass and canopy cover).
77 Both the quantity and quality of resources have been demonstrated to regulate the diversity and
78 community composition of soil microbial communities (Hooper *et al.* 2000; Wardle *et al.* 2004;
79 Schneider *et al.* 2012; Zhou *et al.* 2015). Moreover, microcosm studies have demonstrated that
80 changes in litter quality during decomposition strongly influence the composition and diversity of soil
81 microbial communities (Schneider *et al.* 2012; Zhou *et al.* 2015). Plant diversity could also alter the

82 distribution of microbial communities by promoting a greater diversity of litter types, promoting niche
83 differentiation and resource partitioning (Wardle *et al.* 2004; Gould *et al.* 2016), and facilitating the
84 existence of multiple mutualism (e.g., mycorrhizae and rhizobia) and antagonistic (e.g., plant-
85 pathogen) interactions with soil microbes. Other effects on plant community attributes and functional
86 traits of soil microbes include changes in habitat conditions (e.g., soil structure, shading, water
87 regulation) and soil chemistry (e.g., root exudation and nutrient uptake), which are both known to
88 strongly affect the structure and function of microbial communities (Bardgett 2017; Le Bagousse-
89 Pinguet *et al.* 2017).

90 Plant traits have been used to predict broad-scale shifts in the biomass of fungi and bacteria at
91 the individual plant (Orwin 2010), community (Legay *et al.* 2014) and regional scale (hundreds of
92 kms; de Vries *et al.* 2012; Grigulis *et al.* 2013). Further, plant functional traits are also known to
93 influence the abundance of particular groups of soil microorganisms, such as mycorrhizal fungi (e.g.,
94 López-García *et al.* 2014; 2017), and specific groups involved in N cycling, such as archaeal ammonia
95 oxidisers (Moreau *et al.* 2015; Thion *et al.* 2016). However, the role of plant functional traits in
96 regulating the diversity (number of phylotypes; richness) and community composition (relative
97 abundance of phylotypes) of soil bacteria and fungi remains relatively poorly understood. Recent
98 studies that have evaluated the link between plant functional traits and the taxonomic diversity of soil
99 microbial communities at a local scale have revealed no clear relationships, despite strong effects of
100 plant species identity (Barberán *et al.* 2015; Fry *et al.* 2017; Leff *et al.* 2018). However, whether plant
101 traits can explain variation in microbial diversity and composition at larger spatial scales, and across
102 regions and ecosystem types at the global scale, remains largely unexplored. This is despite the
103 suggestion that the relationship between plant traits and the diversity and community composition of
104 soil microbial communities are likely to be strongest at regional scales (hundreds of kms) where
105 taxonomic and trait diversity is considerable, and the effect of plant attributes on microbial
106 communities could be statistically detected (Wardle 2005). We posit, therefore, that regional scale
107 variation in plant traits will be strongly correlated with changes in diversity and community
108 composition of bacterial and fungal communities.

109 Here, we evaluate the role of plant attributes, including (1) plant community attributes (plant
110 diversity and cover) and (2) functional traits, in predicting the distribution of community composition
111 and diversity of soil bacteria and fungi in two contrasting ecosystem types located in two different
112 hemispheres. Given the strong theoretical link between plant attributes and soil microbial

113 communities, we hypothesized that plant attributes would explain additional variation in microbial
114 community composition and diversity that is unaccounted for by key drivers such as climate or soil
115 properties. Such hypothesis should be valid across regions differing markedly in climate, vegetation
116 and soils. As such, we used two contrasting regional datasets (hundreds of kms) from Australia and
117 England, which included natural forests and a range of grassland types (Fig. S1; de Vries *et al.* 2012;
118 Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016c). The English dataset has previously been used to identify the role of
119 plant traits in predicting the biomass of fungi and bacteria and their relative abundance (de Vries *et al.*
120 2012), but the role of plant attributes as predictors of microbial community composition and diversity
121 remain unaddressed. Our intention was not to merge the two data sets, which differed in their sampling
122 design, vegetation, soil and climatic conditions, and plant trait information, but to test our hypotheses
123 across two regions with markedly different vegetation, climate and soils. In doing so, we provide a
124 general and robust test of the importance of plant traits for explaining regional scale variation in the
125 composition and diversity of soil microbial communities across a range of different ecosystems.

126 **Material and Methods**

127 *Study sites*

128 We used two separate regional datasets (Fig S1). The first included micro-habitat level information on
129 three distinct vegetation classes micro-habitat (grasses, N-fixing shrubs and trees) across twenty
130 natural forest locations from eastern Australia (Fig. S1) (Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016c). Locations
131 in Australia are distributed across a >1000 km environmental transect (Fig. S1). These sites were
132 originally chosen to represent a wide range of aridity conditions, from arid to humid forest
133 communities, and with perennial vegetation cover ranging from 18 to 98%. These ecosystems
134 consistently had independent patches of vegetation dominated by trees (*Eucalyptus* spp.), N-fixing
135 shrubs (*Acacia* spp.), and perennial grasses (*Rhytidosperma* spp.). Total annual precipitation and mean
136 temperature ranged from 280 mm to 1167 mm and from 12.8° C to 17.5°C, respectively. The second
137 dataset was from England and included plot-level information from 180 grasslands varying in
138 management intensity (unimproved, semi-improved and improved grasslands) and covering the main
139 acid, calcicolous, mesotrophic, and wet grassland types of the United Kingdom (see de Vries *et al.*
140 2012 and Manning *et al.* 2015). Locations in England spanned all major grassland regions of the
141 country, distributed across a north to south transect of approximately 500km². Across all grasslands,
142 total annual precipitation and mean temperature ranged from 573 mm to 1355 mm and from 6.3° C to
143 10.2°C, respectively.

144 *Soil sampling*

145 Soil samples from the top ~7cm were collected in Australia and England as explained in Methods S1.
146 In brief, in Australia, three soil cores were collected under the three most common plant functional
147 groups micro-habitat: grasses (*Rhytidosperma* genus including species *R. caespitosum*, *R. pilosum* or
148 *R. racemosum*), N-fixing shrubs (*Acacia* genus including species *A. dealbata*, *A. decora*, *A.*
149 *genistifolia*, *A. implexa* or *A. wilhelmiana*) and trees (*Eucalyptus* genus including species *Eucalyptus*
150 *largiflorens*, *E. microcarpa*, *E. populnea*, *E. rossii*, *E. socialis* or *E. tereticornis*). The same genus of
151 these plant taxa was present across all plots. A total of 60 soil samples (20 sites x three micro-habitats)
152 were collected. Sampling was conducted in March (2014). In England, soil samples were collected
153 June-July 2005 from 180 sites covering the main grassland habitat classifications in the UK, namely
154 acid, calcicolous, mesotrophic, and wet grasslands (De Vries et al. 2012; Manning et al. 2015). The
155 survey covered a wide range of grassland communities within each habitat type and included a total
156 of 256 grassland plant species, confirming the representative nature the national survey (Rodwell
157 1992). In terms of dominant graminoid species, unimproved acid grasslands were typically dominated
158 by *Festuca ovina*, *Deschampsia flexuosa* and *Agrostis capillaris*, calcicolous grasslands were typically
159 dominated by *Festuca rubra*, *Festuca ovina*, *Bromus erectus* and *Carex flacca*; mesotrophic
160 grasslands were typically dominated by *Agrostis canina*, *Festuca rubra*, and *Poa trivialis*; and wet
161 grasslands were dominated by *Carex distichia* and *Molinia caerulea*. Semi-improved grasslands in all
162 four habitat types grasslands became increasingly dominated by *Lolium perenne*, and improved
163 grasslands also strongly promoted *Holcus lanatus* in acid and mestrophic grasslands, *Poa trivialis* in
164 calcicolous grasslands and mesotrophic grasslands, and *Agrostis stolonifera* in wet grasslands.

165 *Climate and soil properties*

166 In all cases, we obtained information on mean annual temperature and Aridity Index (positively related
167 to precipitation)(1km) for the surveyed sites from the Worldclim database (www.worldclim.org).
168 Moreover, we obtained information on total soil organic C, total N and P and pH as explained in
169 Methods S1.

170 *Plant attributes*

171 The Australian and English samples contain shared information on five plant attributes: diversity
172 (species richness), percentage plant cover, Specific Leaf Area (SLA), leaf N content and N fixation
173 (proportion of N fixing plants in England and presence of *Acacia* species –the only N-fixer micro-
174 habitat– in the Australian dataset). In addition, the two datasets include a subset of distinct plant

175 functional traits such as leaf C and P, plant height, canopy width and canopy height in the Australian
176 dataset and leaf dry matter content (LDMC) and relative growth rate (RGR) in the English dataset.
177 Both datasets were originally independently generated and with each study designed to explicitly
178 include variables that were hypothesized to account for variation in soil properties and functions within
179 their respective regions. For example, plant functional traits such as plant height, canopy width and
180 canopy height may explain differences in microbial communities in forests from Australia, but not in
181 English grasslands where they vary little. Detailed information on how plant traits were measured in
182 these two datasets is available in Methods S1.

183 *Soil microbial community*

184 Soil DNA was extracted from both sets of soil samples using the Powersoil® DNA Isolation Kit (Mo
185 Bio Laboratories, Carlsbad, CA, USA). In England, 161 from 180 samples were included in further
186 analyses due to DNA amplification problems. Amplicons targeting the bacterial 16S rRNA gene and
187 fungal ITS2 region were sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq platform and the 341F/805R (bacteria)
188 and FITS7/ITS4 (fungi) primer sets (Methods S1). Bioinformatic analyses were conducted using
189 UPARSE and MOTHUR (Methods S1). Operational Taxonomic Units (OTU) were picked at 97%
190 sequence similarity in both cases. The resulting OTU abundance tables were rarefied. As these
191 analyses were done together for the Australian and English datasets, OTU identities are directly
192 comparable between them.

193 *Statistical analyses*

194 All statistical analyses were independently done for each dataset (Australia and England) and
195 microbial group (bacteria or fungi). First, we evaluated the relationship between bacterial and fungal
196 community dissimilarity with the dissimilarity of plant attributes (plant cover, diversity and functional
197 traits) across plots. To do this, we calculated Bray–Curtis dissimilarities to generate independent
198 community distance matrices at the OTU level for bacterial and fungal communities in the Australia
199 and English datasets. Similarly, the Euclidean distance was used to independently create a matrix of
200 distance for plant drivers for the Australia and English datasets. We then correlated the matrix of plant
201 community attributes and traits distances to the dissimilarity matrix of bacteria and fungi in Australia
202 and England using Mantel test correlations.

203 Second, we used two independent approaches to assess whether plant attributes can predict a
204 unique portion of the variation of soil microbial diversity and community composition. We first
205 conducted Variation Partitioning (R package Vegan; Oksanen *et al.* 2015) as an exploratory analysis

206 to identify whether plant attributes: (1) plant functional traits; and (2) plant diversity and cover, explain
207 a unique portion of the variation in microbial diversity and composition, after accounting for key
208 microbial drivers such as location (latitude and longitude), climate (aridity index and mean annual
209 temperature) and soil properties (total C, N and P and pH; Table 1).

210 We then used a multi-model inference approach based on information theory and non-
211 parametric distance-based linear regressions (DISTLM; McArdle & Anderson 2001) to evaluate
212 whether plant attributes (plant cover, diversity and traits) explained a unique proportion of the
213 variation in bacterial and fungal diversity (richness; number of phylotypes) and community
214 composition (at the OTU level) after accounting for other important microbial drivers such as soil
215 properties (total C, N and P and pH) and climate (aridity index and mean annual temperature). Location
216 (latitude and longitude; Table 1) was included in all models to account for spatial autocorrelation. The
217 Euclidean and Bray-Curtis distances were used for microbial diversity and composition, respectively
218 in these analyses. We carried out these analyses using the PERMANOVA+ for PRIMER statistical
219 package. We ranked all the models that could be generated with different combinations of our
220 independent variables according to the second-order Akaike information criterion (AICc) and
221 considered a $\Delta\text{AICc} > 2$ threshold to differentiate between two substantially different models (Burnham
222 & Anderson 2002). Differences < 2 in AICc between alternative models indicate that they do not differ
223 significantly in their explanatory power. The full statistical reasoning for this approach can be found
224 elsewhere (e.g., Zuur et al. 2009). We then selected the best of those models including all parameters
225 in Table 1, and compared the AICc of the best model with competing models containing: (1) all
226 parameters in model A, but plant functional traits (Model B); (2) included all parameters in model A,
227 but plant community attributes (cover and PDiv) (Model C); or (3) all parameters in model A but plant
228 functional traits and community attributes (Model D) (Table 2).

229 Third, we conducted two independent analyses to assess the importance of plant attributes, soil
230 properties, and climate as predictors of soil microbial community composition and diversity. We first
231 used Random Forest analyses (Archer 2016), as explained in Delgado-Baquerizo et al. (2016a), to
232 identify the most important predictors (Table 1) of bacterial and fungal diversity and community
233 composition. For simplicity, and given that, at this point, we were interested in the responses of the
234 entire microbial community composition rather than on single taxa, in the case of bacterial and fungal
235 community composition, we conducted these analyses on the axes of a NMDS conducted on bacterial
236 and fungal composition data at the lowest taxonomic rank (Fig. S3, stress = 0.08 and = 0.12,

237 respectively). We then used Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to build a system-level
238 understanding of the major direct and indirect effects of climate, soil properties, and plant attributes
239 on the composition and diversity of soil bacteria and fungi (*a priori* model available in Fig. S2 and
240 Methods S1 for details). For simplicity, and due to the data constraints of fitting SE models with many
241 paths, we only included in these models those variables that were identified as major predictors of the
242 diversity and composition of bacteria from the best models of our distance-based multi-model
243 approach. Importantly, in general, similar variables were identified as important predictors in our
244 Random Forest results (see below). Therefore, although we used the same *a priori* model in all cases
245 (Fig. S2), SE models conducted for the different datasets contain different predictors and were
246 constructed independently. The only exception to this was latitude and longitude, which were included
247 in all the models to account for spatial autocorrelation in our models, and to represent other variables
248 that might co-vary with latitude and longitude but which are not included in our analyses. Analyses
249 were performed independently for each dataset. With a good model fit, we were then free to interpret
250 the path coefficients of the model and their associated *P* values. In the case of England we accounted
251 for any effect from management practices on our results, by repeating the SEM analyses using the
252 residuals from a one-way ANOVA in which management practice (managed, intermediate intensity
253 managed, and intensively managed) were treated as a fixed factor and bacterial diversity or
254 composition as a response variable (i.e. residuals of bacterial diversity or composition). This results in
255 a more conservative test of plant effects on microbial communities as functional traits are known to
256 covary with management (see de Vries *et al.* 2012).

257 Finally, we used Random Forest analysis (Archer 2016) to identify the microbial phylotypes
258 that were most strongly associated with a particular plant trait. We focused on shared dominant taxa
259 (>50 reads across all samples) between Australia and England for these analyses. Moreover, we
260 focused on shared plant community attributes (cover and diversity) and functional traits (SLA, leaf N
261 and N fixation), and microbial phylotypes for the Australia and English datasets. Analyses were
262 conducted independently for the Australia and English datasets and for fungal and bacterial
263 communities. For both datasets, we first identified the top unique and shared (significance; $P < 0.05$)
264 microbial phylotypes accounting for the variation of particular plant traits (i.e., those microbial
265 phylotypes that are selected from Random Forest model as important predictors of each plant trait).
266 The reserved approach enabled us to identify particular phylotypes that consistently characterize
267 particular plant attributes in both Australia and England. We then conducted Spearman correlations

268 among shared phylotypes in Australia and England with particular plant traits for which these
269 phylotypes are good predictors. The major goal for these analyses is to provide a list of examples that
270 could make the basis of experimental studies to look at the links between particular microbial
271 phylotypes and plant attributes in more detail.

272 *Data accessibility*

273 Data associated with this paper has been deposited in figshare:
274 <https://figshare.com/s/f61108b8c4fa89074296> (10.6084/m9.figshare.5861061).

275 **Results**

276 *Microbial and plant attributes in Australia and England*

277 The Australia and English datasets varied markedly in fungal and bacterial community composition
278 (Figs. S3-S4). Proteobacteria and Acidobacteria were the dominant bacterial phyla in England, while
279 Actinobacteria was the dominant phylum in Australia (Fig. S4). In both datasets, the fungal community
280 was dominated by Ascomycota (Fig. S4), with Zygomycota and Basidiomycota being the second most
281 abundant fungal phyla in England and Australia, respectively. Fungal diversity was greater in the
282 Australian dataset, but bacterial diversity did not differ between datasets (Fig. S3). See Methods S1
283 for details on the statistical analyses conducted to evaluate these general patterns in microbial diversity
284 and composition. In both datasets, there was considerable heterogeneity in soil properties and
285 microbial communities. For example, in Australia, pH and soil C ranged from 4.8-8.9 and 1.3-12.3%,
286 respectively (Table 1). Similarly, bacterial and fungal diversity ranged from 955-2833 and 489-813
287 phylotypes, respectively. In England, soil pH and C ranged from 4.1-7.8 and 1.4-12.8%, respectively
288 (Table 1), and bacterial and fungal diversity from 820-3329 and 243-763 phylotypes, respectively.

289 Plant attributes varied greatly among plots in both datasets. For example, plant cover ranged
290 from 78.3 to 249.5% (i.e., due to multiple vegetation layers in grassland communities) in England and
291 from 18.3 to 98.3% in Australia. Plant species diversity ranged from 2 to 36 species across grassland
292 plots in England and from 11 to 41 species in forest plots in Australia. Values for CWM SLA ranged
293 from 5.8 to 16.3 cm² g⁻¹ in England and from 6.1 to 127.1 cm² g⁻¹ in Australia, and CWM Leaf N
294 ranged from 1.7 to 3.5% in England and from 0.5 to 2.9% in Australia. The percentage of N fixers in
295 England ranged from 0 to 42.4% of total cover (presence of *Acacia* spp. micro-habitats characterized
296 the only N fixer in the Australian dataset; Table 1).

297 *Linking plant attributes and microbial community composition*

298 The Euclidean matrix of distance for plant attributes were positively and significantly related to Bray-
299 Curtis matrix of distance including the community composition of soil bacteria and fungi in the
300 Australia and English datasets (*via* Mantel test) (Fig. 1), indicating that certain plant community
301 attributes/traits and microbial taxa tend to co-occur in nature. Variation partitioning modeling
302 suggested that, in general, plant attributes explained unique portions of the variation in bacterial and
303 fungal communities from both Australia and England (Fig. 2; Figs. S5 and S6; Table S1). Shared
304 variation explaining microbial community composition and diversity among different predictors (e.g.
305 climate and location, soil properties and plant attributes) cannot be attributed to any of those groups
306 of predictors in particular. Because of this, we only compared the unique portion of the variation in
307 microbial communities explained in a singular manner by either: climate and location, soil properties
308 or plant attributes.

309 Moreover, using distance-based multi-model inference and variation partitioning modeling,
310 we found that plant attributes explained a unique proportion of the variation in soil microbial
311 communities that was unaccounted for by soil properties, climate or location (Table 2). Removal of
312 all plant attributes from these models always resulted in poorer model fit in all cases ($\Delta\text{AIC} > 2.00$). In
313 Australia, our best fitting models selected canopy height, plant cover and leaf P as the major predictors
314 of bacterial community composition and diversity, respectively (Table 2). Plant cover, height and
315 width were selected as major plant predictors of the diversity of soil fungi in Australia (Table 2). The
316 only exception was the community composition of soil fungi in Australia which was best predicted by
317 pH and Aridity Index, and for which models were not improved by the inclusion of plant attributes
318 (Table 2). In England, plant diversity, leaf N and LDMC were selected as major predictors for bacterial
319 composition. The same predictors, but also the cover of N fixers, were also the major drivers of
320 bacterial diversity in this dataset (Table 2). Finally, plant diversity and leaf N were selected as the
321 major predictors of fungal composition, whereas cover, diversity, RGR and SLA were the best
322 predictors of fungal diversity in the English dataset.

323 We then used Random Forest analyses to identify the importance of plant attributes, soil
324 properties and climate in predicting microbial community composition and diversity (Fig. 3). Plant
325 attributes were selected as significant predictors of the diversity and community composition of
326 bacteria and fungi in Australia and England (Fig. 3). In addition, soil properties and climate were key
327 significant predictors of bacterial and fungal attributes; although no soil property or climate variable
328 was selected as a significant driver of the diversity of fungi in Australia. Most predictors in the best

329 fitting models (Table 2) were also selected as significant drivers of bacterial and fungal diversity and
330 community composition by our Random Forest analyses (Fig. 3), thus demonstrating that the identity
331 of the main predictors was robust to the statistical method used.

332 We then used SEM to gain deeper insights on the role of plant attributes and functional traits
333 in predicting the community diversity and composition of fungi and bacteria in two Hemispheres.
334 Each SEM included the predictors of each microbial attribute selected in the best fitting ($\Delta AIC > 2$)
335 models described above and in Table 2. We detected multiple significant direct effects of plant
336 attributes on soil microbial community composition and diversity after accounting for other key
337 drivers such as climate and soil properties (Figs. 4 and 5). In both the Australia and English datasets,
338 plant cover had a negative direct effect on the diversity of bacteria and/or fungi (Fig. 4). In Australia,
339 canopy height was the major plant attribute explaining the composition of bacteria (Fig. 4). In England,
340 plant diversity had a positive effect on the diversity of bacteria and fungi (Fig. 4). Also, plant diversity
341 and leaf N showed direct effects on the composition of bacteria and fungi (Fig. 5).

342 We also identified some indirect effects of location and climate on the composition or diversity
343 of soil bacteria and fungi via plant attributes (Figs. 4 and 5) in the Australian and English datasets. For
344 example, plant width was indirectly related to the composition of fungi *via* changes in soil pH for the
345 Australian dataset (Fig. 4). In addition, we also found direct effects of climate (mainly from Aridity
346 Index) on the diversity of soil bacteria and fungi in England (Fig. 5). Aridity Index also operated via
347 its effects on the plant cover, CWM SLA, and CWM leaf N of temperate grassland plant communities
348 in England, but it did not affect these attributes in Australia (Figs. 4 and 5).

349 Further correlation analyses (Spearman) exploring links among plant attributes and microbial
350 community diversity and composition for Australia and England are available in Fig. S7. Soil pH and
351 C were the most consistent abiotic factors explaining the community composition and/or diversity of
352 fungi and/or bacteria for the Australian and English datasets (Figs 4 and 5). Importantly, in the case
353 of England, the direction and strength of the multiple direct and indirect effects in our SEM were
354 mostly maintained after controlling for management practices by using the residuals of bacterial
355 diversity or composition from a one-way ANOVA, as explained in the Method section (Fig. S8).

356 Finally, we used Random Forest analyses to identify particular bacterial and fungal species
357 that are associated with certain plant community attributes and plant traits in both the Australian and
358 English datasets. A subset of phylotypes (total 57 OTUs) shared by the Australian and English datasets
359 –bioinformatic analyses were done simultaneously for both datasets allowing direct comparison of

360 OTUs– were significantly associated with particular plant traits (Fig. S9). For example, the relative
361 abundance of OTU_1699 (unidentified species from family Ellin5301; phylum *Gemmatimonadetes*)
362 was strongly and positively correlated to N fixation (% coverage of N fixing plants across English
363 grasslands and presence of *Acacia* sp. in Australia) in both the Australian and English datasets
364 ($P < 0.01$). Similarly, the relative abundance of OTU_98 (Unidentified species from genus *Candidatus*
365 *Solibacter*; phylum *Acidobacteria*) was strongly positively related to SLA, in the Australian and
366 English datasets ($P < 0.05$). Finally, the relative abundance of OTU_8 (Uncultured Mortierellaceae;
367 division *Zygomycota*) and the relative abundance of OTU_43313 (Erythrobacteraceae; phylum
368 *proteobacteria*) were found to be strongly negatively related to plant cover and plant diversity,
369 respectively, in both Australia and England (Fig. S9 for complete list of taxa).

370 **Discussion**

371 Our study provides strong observational evidence, from two contrasting regions of the globe that
372 aboveground plant attributes such as diversity, cover and functional traits, can help explain the
373 diversity and community composition of soil bacterial and fungal communities, at a regional scale
374 (hundreds of kilometers). We also provided examples for microbial phylotypes that are strongly
375 related to particular plant traits such as SLA, leaf N, and N fixation across two very different regions
376 of the world. We did this using two separate datasets from Australia and England, which differed
377 markedly in climate (dryland vs. mesic), vegetation (forest vs. grasslands), and microbial community
378 composition (Figs. S3 and S4). Our distance-based and variation partitioning models provided
379 evidence that plant attributes explain a unique proportion of variation in the composition and diversity
380 of microbial communities that is unaccounted for by other key microbial drivers such as climate and
381 soil properties, which are routinely proposed to be the main determinants of microbial community
382 structure and diversity at large spatial scales. Our SEMs provided an integrative understanding of the
383 role of plant attributes in driving soil microbial communities once we controlled for multiple
384 environmental drivers. These results provide further evidence of strong, direct links between particular
385 aboveground plant attributes and the diversity and composition of soil fungal and bacterial
386 communities at regional scales.

387 Our findings accord with the results of microcosm experiments that demonstrate the
388 importance of plant functional traits (e.g. litter chemistry) for soil microbial community composition
389 (Schneider *et al.* 2012; Zhou *et al.* 2015). However, they are in contrast to recent studies that did not
390 find significant relationships between the local distribution of plant traits and soil microbial

391 community composition within Panamanian tropical forest (Barberán *et al.* 2015) or in grassland sites
392 in England (Fry *et al.* 2017; Leff *et al.* 2018). This likely relates to the different spatial scale used in
393 these studies; our study considers variation in microbial communities at a regional scale, whereas
394 studies of Barberán *et al.* (2015), Fry *et al.* (2017) and Leff *et al.* (2018) examined local scales where
395 variation in both plant traits and microbial communities, and their drivers, is less and thus shows
396 weaker patterns of association.

397 Our SEM results indicate that plant cover had a strong negative effect on the diversity of
398 bacteria and/or fungi in both Australia and England. More specifically, our results suggest that
399 increases in percentage plant cover might lead to the exclusion of microbial species via the
400 competition-to-exclusion principle (Eldridge *et al.* 2017). In addition, unlike Australia, in England,
401 plant leaf N content (e.g. positive for bacterial diversity), SLA (e.g. negative for fungal diversity), and
402 species diversity (e.g. positive for fungi and bacteria) were also important drivers of the distribution
403 of the diversity and community composition of fungi and bacteria. All these plant attributes are
404 considered key functional markers which relate to soil fertility and the quantity and quality of plant
405 inputs (Garnier *et al.* 2004). This finding suggests that in temperate grasslands, the community
406 composition and diversity of soil microbial communities may be strongly affected by both the range
407 and quality of the resources entering soil from plant communities, in the form of litter (note that we
408 used leaf nutrients in our study), but they may also be related to an effect of root turnover and exudation
409 (de Vries *et al.* 2012; Grigulis *et al.* 2013). For example, highly diverse plant communities can
410 influence the community composition and diversity of soil microbial communities via greater
411 variability in litter quality (niche partitioning), but also by promoting a higher diversity of resources
412 (e.g. via rhizodeposition; Paterson *et al.* 2007). Plant leaf N and diversity were also major drivers of
413 microbial community composition in the studied grasslands, suggesting that these plant attributes can
414 promote/inhibit the relative abundance of particular microbial taxa. Conversely, other plant traits not
415 measured in England, such as canopy height (likely to be relatively constant in temperate grasslands,
416 and therefore uninformative in England), regulated the community composition of bacteria in
417 Australian forests. Together, the above discussed results suggest that litter quality might be the major
418 plant driver of microbial community composition in temperate grasslands, where plant inputs to soil
419 are relatively large. Further, in the English dataset, there was almost complete vegetation coverage
420 across grassland sites. Conversely in Australia, where plant cover was always less than 100% (18-
421 98%), litter quantity rather than quality likely plays a more important role in influencing the

422 composition of soil microbial communities. We would like to highlight that our study focused on
423 aboveground plant attributes, which were found to account for a unique portion of the variation in the
424 distribution of soil microbial community composition and diversity. However, we did not have
425 available information on belowground attributes for our study sites. As such, we can only guess that
426 including belowground plant attributes would have increased the explanatory power of our models,
427 however, further research need to be done to support this assumption.

428 In addition to demonstrating that plant attributes can explain regional scale variation in
429 bacterial and fungal community composition, our study provides a unique inventory of phylotypes
430 (i.e., species equivalent) that are strongly associated with particular plant traits, such as SLA index,
431 leaf N content and/or N fixation, in two markedly different regions of the globe. This information and
432 approach could be used to: (1) predict the distribution of particular microbial taxa using plant
433 functional traits, with potential implications for the understanding of ecosystem functioning; and (2)
434 help to identify the potential role of certain microbial species, with as yet unestablished functional
435 roles, in driving particular ecosystem functions (e.g. decomposition rates). Some of these phylotypes
436 responded in a similar manner to increases in the values for particular plant traits. For example, the
437 relative abundance of OTU_1699 (family Ellin5301) was strongly positively related to N fixation (%
438 coverage of N fixers across English grasslands and presence of *Acacia* sp. in Australia) in both
439 Australian and English datasets. Regrettably, little is currently known about the ecology of these
440 bacterial taxa. Furthermore, the relative abundance of OTU_98 (*Candidatus Solibacter* sp.) was
441 strongly positively correlated to SLA in both datasets ($p > 0.164$, $P < 0.05$). Species from the genus
442 *Candidatus Solibacter* are known to be chemoorganotrophic organisms that use organic C for growth
443 and energy (Ward *et al.* 2009); as such, they might gain resources from litter inputs, especially those
444 of high decomposability (i.e., often characterized by a higher SLA). In the same vein, OTU_8
445 (*Mortierellaceae* sp), a saprophyte that can act as a facultative parasite (Fitzpatrick and Morton 1930),
446 was negatively related to plant cover in England and Australia (see extended discussion on phylotypes
447 showing opposite patterns in both datasets in Methods S2).

448 Plant attributes such as diversity, vegetation cover, and plant traits are highly sensitive to
449 climate change and land use intensification (Allan *et al.* 2015; García-Palacios *et al.* 2016; Deraison
450 *et al.* 2015; Le Bagousse-Pinguet *et al.* 2017). Supporting this notion, our SEM identified multiple
451 indirect effects of climate on fungal diversity and community composition, driven indirectly by
452 changes in plant attributes. For example, increases in aridity related to changes in plant cover, SLA,

453 and leaf N of temperate grasslands in England, which could be taken to suggest that predicted increases
454 in aridity resulting from climate change (Huang *et al.* 2016) might indirectly alter the diversity and
455 composition of grassland soil fungal communities. In this respect, our SEM results could be used to
456 generate new hypotheses that could potentially lead to management strategies. For instance, our
457 approach could help identify how plant traits mediate climate effects, and lately provide strategies for
458 the management of these traits, that mitigate climate impacts on soil microbial communities and soil
459 processes. This is especially significant given the known importance of changes in fungal communities
460 for biogeochemical cycles and plant community dynamics in grasslands (van der Heijden *et al.* 2008),
461 and hence the potential for this to alter the capacity of these ecosystems to provide essential goods and
462 services, such as food production and climate regulation (Bardgett & van der Putten 2014; Delgado-
463 Baquerizo *et al.* 2016a).

464 Together, our work provides new evidence, from an observational study, for the important role
465 of plant attributes in explaining variation in soil microbial communities across two markedly different
466 mesic and dryland ecosystem types of the world. More precisely, in both forested ecosystems and
467 temperate grasslands, plant attributes explained a unique proportion of the variation in soil microbial
468 communities that could not be explained by factors such as soil abiotic properties and climate. Our
469 findings also advance understanding of the links between plant traits and soil microbial communities
470 by identifying a suite of phylotypes strongly associated with particular plant traits such as SLA, leaf
471 N and N fixation across a broad range of ecosystem types. Such information suggests that it might be
472 possible to predict the distribution of certain microbial taxa at large spatial scales using plant functional
473 traits. Given the importance soil microbial communities for ecosystem functioning, such knowledge
474 is critical to improve our ability to predict likely changes in ecosystem function under global change
475 and to manage terrestrial ecosystems sustainably.

476 **Statement of authorship**

477 M.D-B., R.D.B. and B.K.S. designed this study. The Australia dataset was compiled by D.J.E. and
478 M.D-B. The England dataset was compiled by R.D.B., F.T.V. and P.M. Lab analyses were conducted
479 by E.L.F. and M.D-B. J.K., G.B., D.J.E. and M.D-B. provided plant trait data. B.K.S. provided Miseq
480 Illumina data. K.H. performed bioinformatic analyses. M.D-B. conducted statistical modeling. The
481 manuscript was written by M.D-B with contributions from all co-authors.

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667 **Figure 1.** Relationship between the matrix of dissimilarity from multiple plant traits, cover and
 668 diversity (Euclidean distance) and the beta diversity of bacteria and fungi (community composition
 669 dissimilarity based on Bray-Curtis distance) for the Australia ($n = 60$) and England ($n = \sim 160$) datasets.
 670 The solid lines represent the fitted linear regressions.

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681 **Figure 2.** Relative contribution of the different predictors used to model bacterial and fungal
 682 composition and diversity. Panels represent results from Variation Partitioning modelling aiming to
 683 identify the percentage variance of bacterial and fungal community composition and diversity
 684 explained by plant attributes (cover, diversity and functional traits), soil properties and climate in
 685 Australia and England. Unique and shared variance from plant cover, diversity and functional traits in
 686 predicting microbial community composition and diversity were merged in this figure for simplicity.
 687 An alternative version of this figure showing the unique and shared variance of each group of
 688 predictors can be found in Supplementary Figs. 5 and 6. P-values associated with the relative
 689 contribution of the different predictors are available in Table S1.

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698 **Figure 3.** Random Forest analysis aiming to identify the best individual predictors of the diversity and
 699 community composition of bacteria and fungi in Australia and England. Predictors include plant
 700 attributes, soil properties and climate (Table 1). MSE = Mean Square Error. Community composition
 701 #1 and #2 represent the first and second axis of a NMDS including the community composition of
 702 bacteria or fungi (See Fig. S3).

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704 **Figure 4.** Structural equation model describing the effects of multiple drivers (selected from Table 1)
 705 on the diversity of bacteria (a and c) and fungi (b and d) for the Australia (n = 60) and England (n =
 706 ~160) datasets. Numbers adjacent to arrows are indicative of the effect size of the relationship. R^2
 707 denotes the proportion of variance explained. Climate, soil properties and plant predictors are included
 708 in our models as independent observable variables, however we group them in the same box in the
 709 model for graphical simplicity. All predictors within each both are allowed to co-vary. This does not
 710 apply to model in which only one predictor for a given group is included. In this case, the name of the
 711 predictor stand alone (e.g. soil pH). Significance levels of each predictor are $^{\circ}P < 0.10$, $^*P < 0.05$,
 712 $^{**}P < 0.01$. Negative effects in red.

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Figure 5. Structural equation model describing the effects of multiple drivers (selected from Table 1) on the composition (two axes from a NMDS) of (a and c) and fungi (b and d) for the Australia ($n = 60$) and England ($n = \sim 160$) datasets. Numbers adjacent to arrows are indicative of the effect size of the relationship. R^2 denotes the proportion of variance explained. Climate, soil properties and plant predictors are included in our models as independent observable variables, however we grouped them in the same box in the model for graphical simplicity. Significance levels of each predictor are $^{\circ}P < 0.10$, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$. Negative effects in red.

725 **Table 1.** Complete list of predictors used in this study.

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Group of predictors	Variables	Acronym	Value range (Australia)	Value range (England)	Units
Location	Latitude	Lat	-34.7 to -33.3	50.7 to 54.6	Decimal degrees
	Longitude	Lon	145.7 to 151.1	-4.4 to 0.9	Decimal degrees
Climate	Aridity Index	AI	0.3 to 0.9	0.9 to 2.4	Unitless
	Mean annual temperature	MAT	12.8 to 17.5	6.3 to 10.2	°C
Soil properties	Soil C	C	1.3 to 12.3	1.4 to 12.8	%
	Soil N	N	0.1 to 0.6	0.2 to 1.1	%
	Soil P	P	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $6.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to 0.2	%
Plant community-level traits	pH	pH	4.8 to 8.9	4.1 to 7.8	Unitless
	Plant richness	PDiv	11 to 41	2 to 36	Number of species
	Plant cover	PCov	18.3 to 98.3	78.3 to 249.5	%
Plant functional traits	Specific Leaf Area	SLA	6.1 to 127.1	5.8 to 16.3	cm ² g ⁻¹
	Leaf N N fixation	LN	0.5 to 2.9	1.7 to 3.5	%
		NFix	0 to 1	0 to 0.42	Australia: Presence/Absence N fixers England: Proportion of N fixers (0-1)
	Leaf C	LC	0.5 to 2.9	-	%
	Leaf P	LP	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to 0.2	-	%
	Plant height	PHeight	0.2 to 22.0	-	m
	Canopy width	CWidth	0.1 to 21.0	-	m
	Canopy height	CHeight	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ to 7.0	-	m
	Leaf dry matter content	LDMC	-	14.9 to 34.8	g ⁻¹ g ⁻¹
	Relative growth rate	RGR	-	0.1 to 0.3	g ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ d ⁻¹

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737 **Table 2.** Best-fitting model predicting the distribution of microbial PDiv and composition (bacteria
738 and fungi). Model A include all parameters in Table 1. Model B included all parameters in model A,
739 but plant functional traits. Model C included all parameters in model A, but plant community attributes
740 (cover and PDiv). Model D included all parameters in model A but plant functional traits and
741 community attributes. Location (latitude and longitude) inclusion was forced in all models to account
742 for spatial autocorrelation. Models are ranked by AIC. AIC measures the relative goodness of fit of a
743 given model; the lower its value, the more likely the model to be correct. Δ AIC are difference between
744 the AIC of each model and that of the best model. See Table 1, for the acronyms of the variables
745 included in this table.
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Database	Microbial	Models	Climate	Soil	Plant predictors	R ²	AIC	Δ AIC	
Australia	Bacterial composition	A	AI	pH	CHeight	0.380	451.20	0	
		B	AI	pH		0.334	453.44	2.24	
		C	AI	pH	CHeight	0.380	451.20	0.00	
		D	AI	pH		0.334	453.44	2.24	
	Bacterial richness	A	MAT	C + P	PCov + LP	0.462	283.44	0	
		B	MAT	C + P	PCov	0.441	283.73	0.29	
		C	AI			0.357	286.09	2.65	
		D	AI			0.357	286.09	2.65	
	Fungal composition	A		AI		CWidth	0.172	497.37	
		B		AI	pH		0.170	497.55	0.18
		C		AI		CWidth	0.172	497.37	0.00
		D		AI	pH		0.170	497.55	0.18
	Fungal richness	A			C + N + pH	PCov + PHeight + CWidth	0.222	218.51	
		B			C + N + pH	PCov	0.159	219.13	0.62
		C			pH		0.049	220.82	2.31
		D			pH		0.049	220.82	2.31
	England	Bacterial composition	A	AI + MAT	C + N + pH	PDiv + LN + LDMC	0.412	1150.00	
			B	AI + MAT	C + N + P + pH	PDiv	0.394	1152.60	2.60
			C	AI + MAT	C + N + pH	RGR + LN + LDMC	0.406	1151.70	1.70
			D	AI + MAT	C + N + P + pH		0.377	1155.10	5.10
Bacterial richness		A	AI + MAT	C + N + pH	PDiv + RGR + LN + LDMC + NFix	0.485	647.88		

	B	AI + MAT	C + N + P + pH		0.360	673.52	25.64
	C	AI + MAT	C + N + pH	LDMC + NFix	0.459	649.27	1.39
	D	AI + MAT	C + N + P + pH		0.360	673.52	25.64
Fungal composition	A	AI	C + pH	PDiv + LN	0.233	1269.70	
	B	AI	C + pH	PDiv	0.237	1270.90	1.20
	C	AI	C + pH	RGR + LN + LDMC	0.237	1271.10	1.40
	D	AI	C + pH		0.215	1273.50	3.80
Fungal richness	A	AI	C + pH	PCov + PDiv + RGR + SLA	0.282	802.24	
	B	AI	C + pH	PCov + PDiv	0.250	805.05	2.81
	C	AI	C + pH	RGR + SLA	0.240	807.25	5.01
	D	AI	C + pH		0.210	809.37	7.13

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768 **Supplementary Information**

769 **Methods S1.** Supplementary Methods.

770 **Methods S2.** Extended discussion on particular microbial phylotypes associated with particular plant
771 functional traits.

772 **Table S1.** P-values associated to the relative contribution of the different predictors used to model the
773 richness and community composition of bacteria and fungi in Australia and England.

774 **Figure S1.** Locations of the sites included in this study for the Australia and England datasets.

775 **Figure S2.** A priori structural equation model including direct and indirect effects of geographical
776 location, climate, soil properties and plant attributes on the community composition or richness of soil
777 bacteria and fungi.

778 **Figure S3.** Community composition and diversity of bacteria and fungi for the Australia and England
779 datasets.

780 **Figure S4.** Composition of bacteria and fungi at the phyla level for the Australia and England datasets.

781 **Figure S5.** Variation partitioning modeling aiming to identify the relative contribution of (1) plant
782 traits, (2) plant diversity and cover, (3) location and climate and (4) soil properties as predictors of the
783 composition of bacteria and fungi at the OTU level.

784 **Figure S6.** Variation partitioning modeling aiming to identify the relative contribution of (1) plant
785 traits, (2) plant diversity and cover, (3) location and climate and (4) soil properties as predictors of the
786 diversity of bacteria and fungi at the OTU level.

787 **Figure S7.** Correlations between plants traits, cover and diversity with the diversity and composition
788 of bacteria and fungi for the Australia and England datasets.

789 **Figure S8.** Structural equation model describing the effects of multiple drivers on the residuals of
790 diversity and community composition of bacteria and fungi for the England dataset.

791 **Figure S9.** Shared phylotypes in the Australia and England dataset that were found to be universal
792 predictors (via Random Forest analyses) of multiple plant attributes including plant community
793 attributes (cover and richness) and traits (SLA index, N fixation and leaf N).

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799 **Supplementary Information**

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801 **Plant attributes explain the distribution of soil microbial communities in two**
802 **contrasting regions of the globe.**

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804 Manuel Delgado-Baquerizo, Ellen L. Fry, David J. Eldridge, Franciska T. de Vries, Pete Manning,
805 Kelly Hamonts, Jens Kattge, Gerhard Boenisch, Brajesh K. Singh, Richard D. Bardgett.

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811 **This PDF file includes:**

812 Methods S1-S2

813 Table S1

814 Figures S1-S9

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829 **Methods S1.** Supplementary Methods.

830 *Soil sampling*

831 In Australia, soil samples were collected in March 2014. A 30 m x 30 m site representative of the
832 dominant vegetation was established at 20 locations across New South Wales. At each site, three soil
833 cores (0-5 cm depth) were collected under the three most common plant functional groups micro-
834 habitat: grasses (*Rhytidosperma* spp.), N-fixing shrubs (*Acacia* spp.) and trees (*Eucalyptus* spp.). The
835 same genus of these plant taxa was present across all plots. A total of 60 soil samples (20 sites x three
836 functional group micro-habitats) were collected in this study. Soil cores were then mixed to obtain a
837 composite soil sample per micro-habitat for each of the sites. Following field sampling, the soil was
838 separated into two fractions. A fraction of the soil was immediately frozen at -20 °C for molecular
839 analyses.

840 In England, sampling was conducted in June/July 2005. The sites consisted of triplets of
841 extensively managed, intermediate intensively managed, and intensively managed grasslands at 60
842 locations giving 180 sites. At each of these a 25 m x 25 m plot of homogenous vegetation was
843 established and five soil cores (0-7 cm depth) were taken at random and pooled to produce a composite
844 sample for microbial and chemical analysis. Following field sampling, the soil was sieved (2 mm
845 mesh) and separated into two fractions, one of which was immediately frozen at -80 °C for molecular
846 analyses.

847 *Climate*

848 *In all cases, we obtained information on mean annual temperature and precipitation (1 km) for the*
849 *surveyed sites from the Worldclim database (www.worldclim.org).* In addition, for each site we
850 obtained the Aridity Index (Precipitation/evapotranspiration) from the Global Potential
851 Evapotranspiration database (Zomer *et al.* 2008), which is based on interpolations provided by
852 WorldClim. We used Aridity Index (which is positively related to precipitation) rather than mean
853 annual precipitation because aridity includes both mean annual precipitation and potential
854 evapotranspiration, and is therefore a more accurate metric of the water availability at each site.

855 *Soil properties*

856 For the Australian samples, concentration of soil total organic carbon (C) was determined as described
857 in Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* (2016c). *Soil total N was measured with a CN analyzer (Leco CHN628*
858 *Series, LECO Corporation, St Joseph, MI, USA) and total phosphorus (P) was measured using a*
859 *SKALAR San++ Analyzer (Skalar, Breda, The Netherlands) after digestion with sulphuric acid. For*

860 the English samples, total soil C and N were measured on an Elementar Vario EL elemental analyzer
861 (Hanau, Germany), and soil P was measured by combustion and digestion in sulfuric acid, followed
862 by quantification of orthophosphate by automated colorimetry. In all cases, soil pH was measured in
863 a soil and water suspension with a pH meter.

864 *Plant attributes*

865 The Australia dataset includes *de novo* information on eight plant traits for multiple genus
866 corresponding with the three sampled micro-habitat in each plot: grasses (*Rhytidosperma*
867 spp.), N-fixing shrubs (*Acacia* spp.) and trees (*Eucalyptus* spp.). These plant traits include leaf C, N
868 and P, SLA index, plant height, canopy width, canopy height (distance from canopy to ground), and
869 ability to fix N (hereafter N fixation). The concentrations of leaf C, N and P for *Rhytidosperma* spp.,
870 *Acacia* spp., and *Eucalyptus* spp. were determined using the same methods explained above for soil.
871 In all cases, a composite sample from ten individuals was collected per plot. Average plant height,
872 width and canopy height and ability to fix N were determined in the field for each plot. We used a
873 clinometer to measure the height of all large trees (> 2m) and a graduated pole to measure trees and
874 shrubs less than 2 m tall. SLA was measured in the lab using a standardized protocol (Cornelissen *et*
875 *al.* 2003) and N fixation was measured as presence of *Acacia* species (the only N-fixer micro-habitat
876 in this dataset). Total plant cover and diversity (number of species) were recorded at each site as
877 explained in Maestre *et al.* (2015). Note that in this dataset, sampling effort was focused on dominant
878 plants –which are expected to affect microbial communities via their plant attributes and functional
879 traits–, however, other less dominant species were also present in these plots allowing us to obtain a
880 metric of plant diversity per plot.

881 In England, we used the plant functional trait dataset of de Vries *et al.* (2012), which included
882 community weighted mean (CWM) values for five plant traits which were assigned to all plant species
883 occurring in the 180 plots: leaf dry matter content (LDMC), relative growth rate (RGR), leaf N content
884 (LNC), SLA, and proportion of N-fixer plants (hereafter N fixation). In each site, the plant cover of
885 all vascular plant species, total plant cover and species richness were recorded in five 1m² quadrates
886 and averaged (de Vries *et al.* 2012). Cover data were also combined with trait data obtained from the
887 TRY database (Kattge *et al.* 2008) to determine community abundance (plant cover) weighted means
888 of each trait (CWMs), following de Vries *et al.* (2012); information on the cover of N-fixing plant
889 species was also gathered for each plot.

890 *Sequence data processing*

891 After visual assessment of the quality of all Illumina R1 and R2 reads using FastQC (Andrews 2010),
892 low quality regions ($Q < 20$) were trimmed from the 5' end of the sequences (20 bp from R1 and 82 bp
893 from R2 for primer set 341F/805R; 5 bp from R1 and 35 bp from R2 for primer set FITS7-ITS4R)
894 using SEQTK (<https://github.com/lh3/seqtk>). The paired ends were subsequently joined using FLASH
895 (Magoc & Salzberg 2011). Remaining primer sequences were removed from the resulting reads using
896 SEQTK and a further round of quality control was conducted in mother (Ward *et al.* 2009) to discard
897 short sequences (< 380 bp for 16S and < 150 bp for ITS), as well as sequences with ambiguous
898 characters or more than 8 homopolymers. Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) were built at 97%
899 sequence similarity using UPARSE (Edgar *et al.* 2013). Singletons were discarded, as well as chimeric
900 sequences identified by the UCHIME algorithm using the recommended SILVA gold 16S rRNA gene
901 or UNITE reference databases for bacteria and fungi, respectively. OTU abundance (Edgar *et al.* 2011)
902 tables were constructed by running the `usearch_global` command (<http://www.drive5.com/>).
903 Taxonomy was assigned to OTUs in mothur using the naïve Bayesian classifier with a minimum
904 bootstrap support of 60% and the Greengenes database version 13_8 (DeSantis *et al.* 2006; McDonald
905 *et al.* 2012) for bacteria or the dynamic UNITE version 6 dataset (Koljalg *et al.* 2013) for fungi. The
906 resulting OTU abundance tables were rarefied to an even number of sequences per sample,
907 corresponding to the minimum number of sequences for a single soil sample (13225 sequences/sample
908 for bacteria and 13433 sequences/sample for fungi), using mother (Schloss *et al.* 2009). We further
909 removed phylotypes that only had one read per OTU across all samples.

910 *General patterns in microbial diversity and composition*

911 We first examined the community composition and diversity (number of species) of bacteria and fungi
912 in the Australian and English datasets. To obtain a metric of microbial community composition at the
913 OTU level, we used a non-metric multidimensional ordination (NMDS). Fungal and bacterial
914 community compositions were analysed separately, but in both cases, simultaneously included data
915 from the Australia and English datasets. We retained the first two axes from a 2D solution (stress ~
916 0.1 in all cases). We conducted NMDS ordinations with the package `Vegan` from R (Oksanen *et al.*
917 2015) using the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index. We evaluated overall differences in microbial
918 diversity and composition between the Australia and English dataset by conducting one-way
919 PERMANOVA with dataset (Australia/England) as a fixed factor. The PERMANOVA aiming to
920 assess overall differences in microbial community composition between datasets was carried out
921 including information at the OTU level and not the axes of the NMDS. These analyses were done

922 using the PERMANOVA+ for PRIMER statistical package (PRIMER-E Ltd., Plymouth Marine
923 Laboratory, UK).

924 *Structural Equation Modeling.*

925 Unlike regression or ANOVA, SEM offers the ability to separate multiple pathways of influence and
926 view them as parts of a system, and thus is useful for investigating the complex relationships among
927 predictors commonly found in natural ecosystems (Grace 2006). The probability that a path coefficient
928 differs from zero was tested using bootstrap resampling. Bootstrapping is preferred to the classical
929 maximum-likelihood estimation in these cases because in bootstrapping probability assessments are
930 not based on the assumption that the data match a particular theoretical distribution.

931 The goodness of fit of SEM models was checked using the following: the Chi-square test, the
932 root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) and the Bollen-Stine bootstrap test (Schermelel-
933 Engel *et al.* 2003). Our *a priori* models attained an acceptable/good fit by all criteria in all cases, and
934 thus no post hoc alterations were made. SEM models were conducted with the software AMOS 20
935 (IBM SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, USA).

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937 **Methods S2.** *Extended discussion on particular microbial phylotypes associated with particular plant*
938 *functional traits.*

939 Other phylotypes showed opposite patterns in both datasets, but were still characteristic of particular
940 plant traits (see the complete list of examples in Table S1). Examples include OTU_10654 (family
941 Rhodospirillaceae) or OTU_4 (*Arthrobacter oxydans*) as bacteria associated with SLA or OTU_3517
942 (*Catenulostroma hermanusense*; plant pathogen) and OTU_3470 (*Acremonium R8_9*; saprophyte) as
943 fungi linked to leaf N. These inconsistencies may be related to the strong differences between the
944 Australian and English datasets in terms of vegetation, or to the capturing of two sides of a unimodal,
945 or other non-linear relationship, as CWM values of some plant traits (e.g. SLA index and leaf N) were
946 very different between the two regions (García-Palacios *et al.* 2013).

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952 **Table S1.** P-values associated to the relative contribution of the different predictors used to model the
953 richness and community composition of bacteria and fungi in Australia and England.

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Dataset	Microbial attributes	Plant traits	Plant diversity + cover	Soil properties	Location + climate
Australia	Bacterial richness	0.627	0.002	0.003	< 0.001
	Bacterial composition	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	Fungal richness	0.991	0.230	0.308	0.789
	Fungal composition	0.002	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
England	Bacterial richness	0.001	0.770	0.005	0.053
	Bacterial composition	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	Fungal richness	0.831	0.003	< 0.001	< 0.001
	Fungal composition	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001

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961 **Figure S1.** Locations of the sites included in this study for the Australia ($n = 60$) and England ($n \sim 160$)

962 datasets.

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969 **Figure S2.** A priori structural equation model including direct and indirect effects of geographical
970 location, climate, soil properties and plant attributes on the community composition or richness of soil
971 bacteria and fungi.

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Figure S3. Community composition (a-b) and diversity (mean \pm SE; c-d) of bacteria and fungi for the Australia ($n = 60$) and England ($n \sim 160$) datasets.

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Figure S4. Composition of bacteria and fungi at the phyla level for the Australia (n = 60) and England (n ~160) datasets.

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1021 **Figure S5.** Variation partitioning modeling aiming to identify the relative contribution of (1) plant
 1022 traits, (2) plant diversity and cover, (3) location and climate and (4) soil properties as predictors of the
 1023 composition of bacteria (a and c) and fungi (b and d) at the OTU level. Shared effects of these variable
 1024 groups are indicated by the overlap of circles. Only >0% portions of explained variation are plotted.

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Figure S6. Variation partitioning modeling aiming to identify the relative contribution of (1) plant traits, (2) plant diversity and cover, (3) location and climate and (4) soil properties as predictors of the diversity of bacteria (a and c) and fungi (b and d) at the OTU level. Shared effects of these variable groups are indicated by the overlap of circles. Only >0% portions of explained variation are plotted.

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 1048 **Figure S7.** Correlations (Pearson) between plants traits, cover and diversity with the diversity and
 1049 composition (two axes from a NMDS) of bacteria and fungi for the Australia (a; n = 60) and England
 1050 (b; n = ~160) datasets. Significance levels of each predictor are *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01.

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Figure S8. Structural equation model describing the effects of multiple drivers (selected from Table 1) on the residuals of diversity (a and b) and community composition (c and d) of bacteria and fungi for the England (n = ~160) dataset. Numbers adjacent to arrows are indicative of the effect size of the relationship. R² denotes the proportion of variance explained. Climate, soil properties and plant predictors are included in our models as independent observable variables, however we grouped them in the same box in the model for graphical simplicity. Significance levels of each predictor are °P < 0.10, *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01.

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1070 **Figure S9.** Shared phylotypes in the Australia and England dataset that were found to be universal
 1071 predictors (via Random Forest analyses) of multiple plant attributes including plant community
 1072 attributes (cover and richness) and traits (SLA index, N fixation and leaf N). Functional traits from
 1073 fungal communities were identified using the FUNGUILD database
 1074 (<http://www.stbates.org/guilds/app.php>). This Figure shows importance (MSE = Mean square error)
 1075 for each microbial phylotype selected from Random Forest analyses as predictors of particular plant
 1076 traits and correlation (Spearman $P < 0.05$) between microbial phylotypes and plant traits.

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